

Ethnopharmacological application of animals among the people of Mamtaz Abad, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

Various animal body parts have been utilized in the conservation and defense of human health disorders since the beginning of time, and such therapies are known as zoo therapy. Zootherapy has a long history and a vast terrestrial distribution. It has been said that the traditional healer have been using animals to treat various diseases for over 4,000 years. Many species of animals have been recognized in folklore remedies, which are utilized to heal a variety of ailments. A study was designed to learn about the ethnomedicinal use of animals in Mumtaz Abad. Data were collected from 100 male respondents. During surveys noted that most of the respondents are literate and while other are illiterate. Respondents having different occupations i.e. govt. employers, teachers, students, housewives, farmers, shopkeepers and homeopathic doctors and most of the people belong to 18 to 40 ages. Fat, meat, egg, milk and semen used to treat joint pain, backbone pain, paralysis, asthma problem, fever, cough, weakness, asthma, burnt, kidney pain, vitamin B, asthma, liver, joint pain and backbone pain.

Keywords: Zootherapy, Ethnomedicine, Animals, human, Kashmir

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INTRODUCTION

Since ancient times, many wild and native animal body parts have been utilized in the conservation and defense of human sicknesses (Adeola, 1992), and these rehabilitations are known as zoo therapy (Costa-Neto, 2005b). Animal based therapy has a long history and a vast terrestrial distribution. It has been said that the Chinese have been using animals to treat various diseases for over 4,000 years (Zhang and Wang, 1992). Lots of animals have been identified in folklore Medicines, which are utilized to cure a variety of ailments (Alves and Rosa, 2005). In India, around 15 to 20% of traditional medicines derived from animals are used to cure various diseases (Unnikrishnan, 1998), and almost 500 species of invertebrates are used to treat various diseases (Oudhia, 1995).

Stroking, stroking, viewing, and interacting with diverse faunas can be soothing, reduce heart rate and stroke risk, and be physiologically beneficial (DePrekl, 2002). To regain fitness, humans have used chemicals derived from faunas and floras (Agosta, 1996). Indeed, faunas as remedial mediators have made significant contributions to illness cure over the world (Costa-Neto and Marques,

2000). It is predicted that 8.7 percent of the key compounds used in medications are derived from animals (Dedeke et al., 2006). Pests are important components of novel medications because of their painkiller, antibacterial, immunological, anaesthetic, anti-rheumatic, and diuretic capabilities (Yamakawa, 1998). Chitosan, a pest exoskeleton product, is applied as to “lower cholesterol”, as an “anticoagulant”, and to recover tissues (Goodman, 1989). Promising anticancer medicines have been isolated from the parts of butterflies and beetles (Launet, 1993; Kunin and Lawton, 1996). The viper, for example, generates angiotensin converting enzyme, a hormone that cleaves angiotensin 1 to make angiotensin 2, which induces vasoconstriction and elevated blood pressure (Bisset, 1991). Similarly, amphibians release a number of chemical substances with defensive properties, including as peptides, alkaloids, biogenic amines, and steroids (Daly, 2003). These chemical compounds have a variety of medical effects, including neurotoxic, cardiotoxic, and myotoxic properties (Clarke, 1997).

Different body parts of animals like meat (Haidar and Bashir, 2021), egg (Tariq, 2020), milk (Aslam and Faiz, 2020), venom (Altaf and Faiz, 2021), fats, oil (Ijaz and Faiz, 2021), feather (Adil and Tariq, 2020), bile, and other parts used to treat various diseases (Fabricant and Farnsworth, 2001; Costa-Neto, 2005a; Muhammad *et al.*, 2017a; Muhammad *et al.*, 2017b; Aslam and Faiz, 2020; Ijaz *et al.*, 2020; Mughal *et al.*, 2020; Ijaz and Iftikhar, 2021; Saleem *et al.*, 2021; Saeed *et al.*, 2022; Umair *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, the spread of new medications is based on native communities' traditional awareness. As a result, documenting of native people's customary knowledge is critical, because contemporary medicine's growth has recently been hampered by the loss of socioeconomic and cultural characteristics of native groups of people all over the world (Alves and Rosa, 2005). Pakistan's wildlife is rich, with 668 "species of birds" (Mirza and Wasiq, 2007), 5000 "species of insects" (Ali, 1998), and over 1000 "species of marine and fresh water fishes," 195 "species of herptiles" (Khan, 2004), and 195 "species of mammals" (Roberts, 1997).

Varieties of these plants are utilized for medicinal reasons in various civilizations (Muhammad *et al.*, 2017; Umair *et al.*, 2017). However, ethno-medicine (Bijalwan *et al.*, 2011; Altaf, 2016; Altaf *et al.*, 2017; Bashir *et al.*, 2018; Umair and Yaqoob, 2018; Abbas *et al.*, 2020; Adil and Tariq, 2020; Altaf *et al.*, 2020; Altaf and Umair, 2020; Mughal *et al.*, 2020; Tariq, 2020; Abbasi, 2021; Altaf *et al.*, 2021; Haidar and Bashir, 2021; Zainab, 2021; Faiz *et al.*, 2022; Rahman *et al.*, 2022) and modern medicine (Akhtar, 2021; Nazir, 2021) uses of fauna have received little attention. In addition, we believe that ethnoherpetological information of local groups residing in established regions is at risk due to “urbanization”, “industrialization”, and “population growth”, and that it should be recorded before it is lost. As a result, the current study sought to assess and record ethnopharmacological usage of fauna among the residents of Mamta Abad, Azad Jammu and Kashmir.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Haveli is “162 kilometres” from Muzaffarabad, the capital of Azad Kashmir. It is “250 kilometres” from Islamabad, Pakistan's capital. The entire district Haveli is a hilly territory with a general inclination from northeast to south-west. The region is part of the lower Himalayas zone. Pir- Panjal is the district's primary range. The Haji-

Pir Pass is located at an elevation of “3421 metres above sea level”. The elevation ranges from “1500 to 2500 metres above sea level”. Coniferous trees cover the majority of the mountains (Figure 1).

Data were gathered from 100 farmers, herders, hunters, instructors, and desi hakeem or “traditional healer”. Informers were selected based on their expertise of animal medical applications. The “Mammals”, “birds”, “herpetofauna” and “ichthyofauna” were categorized utilizing field guides “*Mammals of Pakistan*” (Roberts, 2005a, b), “*Birds of Pakistan*” (Roberts, 1991, 1992), “*Amphibian and Reptiles of Pakistan*” (Khan, 2006) and “*Freshwater Fishes of Pakistan*” (Mirza, 2004).

Figure 1: Map of the Study Area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data were gathered from male respondents (100). During surveys, it was discovered that the majority of respondents are literate, while others are illiterate. Respondents work in a variety of vocations, including government employers, teachers, students, housewives, farmers, merchants, and homoeopathic physicians, and the majority are between the ages of 18 and 40 (Figure 2).

Fat, meat, egg, milk, and sperm were used to cure joint pain, backbone pain, paralysis, asthma, burns, kidney pain, vitamin B, asthma, liver, joint pain, and backbone pain (Table 4.1). The common quail is used to treat bilious disorders, regulate heartbeat, tuberculosis, joint pain, back bone pain, and paralysis; nevertheless, prior research has shown that this species is used to treat skin diseases, anaemia, body weakness, improve memory, sexual power, and fever (Lohani, 2011; Vijayakumar *et al.*, 2015a; Vijayakumar *et al.*, 2015b; Altaf *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 2: Respondents of profile.

Table 1: Ethnopharmacological application of animals among the people of Mamtaz abad, Azad Jammu and Kashmir.

Sr.	Common name	Part Used = Mode of Application	Diseases	Respondents number
1	<i>Bungarus caeruleus</i> Schneider, 1801 “Common krait” Kala sup	Fat=Topical	Joint pain, backbone pain	5
2	<i>Daboia russelii russelii</i> Shaw and Nodder, 1797 “Russell's chain viper” Sap	Fat=Topical	Joint pain, aging	2
3	<i>Laudakia agrorensis</i> Stoliczka, 1872 “Agor agama” Sandaila	Fat=Topical	Joint pain, aging	2
4	<i>Varanus bengalensis</i> Daudin, 1802 “Bengal monitor” Kehskarow	Fat=Topical	Backbone pain , joint pain	1
5	<i>Naja oxiana</i> Eichwald, 1837 “Brown cobra” Chajla sup	Skin=Topical	Joint pain, aging	2

6	<i>Coturnix coturnix</i> (Linnaeus, 1758 "Common quail" Batair	Meat=Oral	Paralysis, asthma problem	7
7	<i>Columba livia</i> (Gmelin, 1789) "Common Pigeon" Jungli Kabotar	Meat=Oral	Paralysis, pneumonia	11
8	<i>Streptopelia orientalis</i> (Latham, 1790) "Oriental Turtle Dove" Fakhta	Meat=Oral	Wound	12
9	<i>Spilopelia chinensis</i> (Scopoli, 1786) "Spotted Dove" Fakhta	Meat=Oral	Wound	12
10	<i>Passer domesticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) "House Sparrow" Chiri	Meat and Egg=Oral	Fever, cough, weakness, asthma	14
11	<i>Passer cinnamomeus</i> (Tessminck, 1836) "Russet Sparrow" Jungli Chiri	Meat=Oral	Fever, cough, weakness, asthma	14
12	<i>Gallus gallus domesticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) Hen Murgghi	Meat and egg=Oral	Burnt, kidney pain	21
13	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i> <i>domesticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) Duck Batakh	Feather=Oral	Vitamin B, asthma, liver	23
14	<i>Panthera pardus</i> <i>Linnaeus, 1758</i> Common Leopard Cheetah/tanduwa	Fat=Topical	Joint pain, backbone pain	8
15	<i>Suncus murinus</i> <i>Linnaeus, 1758</i> House shrew Choa	Fat=Topical	Joint pain	2
16	<i>Hystrix indica</i> <i>Kerr, 179</i> Indian Crested Porcupine, Say	Meat= Topical	Wound	2
17	<i>Macaca mulatta</i>	Fat= Topical	Impotency, joint	3

	<i>Zimmermann, 1780</i>		pain, backbone pain	
	Rhesus Macaque			
	Bndar/Bojo			
18	<i>Canis aureus</i>		Impotency, joint	3
	<i>Linnaeus, 1758</i>	Fat= Topical	pain, backbone pain	
	Asiatic jackal			
	Gedar			
19	<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>		Impotency, joint	3
	<i>Linnaeus, 1758</i>	Fat= Topical	pain, backbone pain	
	Red fox			
	Phand			
20	<i>Capra aegagrus hircus</i>		Weakness, , irregular	11
	<i>(Linnaeus, 1758)</i>	Milk and	menstrual cycle	
	Goat	Meat=Oral		
	Bakri			
21	<i>Bos taurus</i>		Vitamin E, Zinc	14
	<i>(Linnaeus, 1758)</i>	Milk and		
	Cow	Meat=Oral		
	Gay			
22	<i>Equus caballus</i>		Tetanus	7
	<i>(Linnaeus, 1758)</i>	Semen =T		
	Horse			
	Ghura			
23	<i>Camelus dromedaries</i>		Used for hepatitis C,	13
	<i>(Linnaeus, 1758)</i>	Milk=O	kidney problems	
	Camel			
24	<i>Bubalus bubalis</i>		Yogurt, digestion	14
	<i>(Linnaeus, 1758)</i>	Milk and		
	Buffalo	Meat=Oral		
	Maj			
25	<i>Apporactodea spp.</i>		Measles	3
	Savigny, 1826	Whole		
	Earthworm	body=Oral		
26	<i>Apis spp.</i>		Cough, asthma	21
	<i>Linnaeus, 1758</i>	Honey=Oral		
	European honey bee			
	Shahd Makhi			

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